

Use of a MDI-functionalized reactive polymer for the manufacture of modified bitumen with enhanced properties for roofing applications.

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Martín-Alfonso, M. J., Partal, P., Navarro, F. J., García-Morales, M., & Gallegos, C. (2008)

Departamento de Ingeniería Química, Facultad de Ciencias Experimentales, Campus "El Carmen", Universidad de Huelva, 21071 Huelva, Spain

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Abstract

In this study, the suitability of a reactive polymer, synthesized by reaction of 4,4'-diphenylmethane diisocyanate (MDI) with a low molecular weight polyethylene-glycol (PEG), as a modifying agent for the manufacture of bitumen-based waterproof membranes, was evaluated. With that purpose, rheological and thermal analysis tests, and microstructural observations by AFM were carried out on different samples of modified bitumen having a MDI-PEG content ranging from 0 to 10 wt.%, cured at room temperature for a period of time within 0-30 days. The results obtained demonstrate that the addition of the reactive polymer proposed in this work to bitumen is very suitable at high in-service temperatures, because a noticeable increase in the values of viscosity, at 60 C, of the resulting modified bitumen samples is observed on a timescale of days. AFM observations, carried out at 50 C, evidenced that the reactive polymer MDI-PEG leads to a new microstructure, displaying a higher level of stiffness. Therefore, this polymer should be seriously taken into consideration as a modifier of bituminous coatings for the waterproofing industry.

Keywords: Modified bitumen; Reactive polymer; Rheology; Roofing membrane; Product design.

F 1. Viscous flow curves, at 60°C, for 8 wt.% MDI-PEG modified bitumen, as a function of curing time (A), and for MDI-PEG.

F 2. Evolution of the Newtonian viscosity with curing time, as a function of MDI-PEG concentration.

F 3. Evolution of R&B softening temperature with MDI-PEG concentration, as a function of curing time.

F 4. Frequency dependence, at 20°C, of the storage and loss moduli, as a function of curing time, for a selected PMB containing 8 wt.% MDI-PEG.

F 5. Reversing heat flow curves for selected MDI-PEG modified bitumen samples after a curing period of 30 days, as a function of polymer concentration.

F 6. Non-reversing heat flow curves for selected MDI-PEG modified bitumen samples after a curing period of 30 days, as a function of polymer concentration.

F 7. AFM micrographs, at 50 °C, for the neat bitumen (A), as well as for modified bitumen samples containing 2 wt.% (B), 8 wt.% (C) and 10 wt.% (D) of MDI-PEG, after a period of curing of 11 months (micrograph dimensions: 50x50 nanom).